

Building a model for the predictive improvement of air quality in Circular Smart cities

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Abstract— A smart city that implements the principles of the Circular Economy (CE) is called a Circular and Smart city. One of the dimensions that make up a CE, one with great weight and importance, is the management of emissions, which in the specific case of cities affects air quality and health of citizens. This work proposes a smart management model for air quality in smart circular cities, in which the various factors that condition it are integrated. In this intelligent management model, data is collected and the application of Artificial Intelligence algorithms is proposed on these data. They not only perform an analysis of the current state of the air, but also allow predictive information to be obtained on how air quality will evolve in the future, an aspect that would allow those responsible for sustainable circular cities to make appropriate decisions.

Keywords—Smart circular cities, circular economy, air quality, measurement, AI, prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

In the times we live, cities, fundamental elements of our society, face a profound transformation as a result of technological innovations that have emerged through the centuries. The intensive application of these innovations has given rise to Smart Cities [1] [2]. Thus, with the aim of creating smart cities, information technologies are being intensively applied in cities to management models, in order to be more efficient in managing their resources, providing better services to citizens [3]. In addition, cities are increasingly considering the adoption of sustainability principles in their management [4] [5]. Sustainable circular cities serve both purposes [4].

Thus, the digital transformation of cities is reaching various areas: (1) their management, offering citizens adequate leadership with a long-term strategic vision of the city, where Information Technologies play an important role (for example, intelligent management of strategic resources such as traffic, water, or vegetation, among many others); (2) the incorporation of technological tools that allow electronic and participatory government, all from an efficient management perspective, including intelligent management of the economy, industrial development, tourism, and marketing; and (3) using Information Technologies to deal with decisions related to life in the territory, mobility management, security and emergency management, and the services provided of a cultural, social, inclusive, and leisure nature. All such transformation will be addressed in Smart Circular Cities from a digital perspective that considers principles of

economic, social, and environmental sustainability (ESG) of the city, preserving the environment and natural resources. Also, through the use of Information Technology, efficient information management will be achieved by striking a balance between the areas supported by the application of new Information Technologies; for example, creating networks in cities that allow fluid and sustainable communication, applying Artificial Intelligence to their management, Cloud Computing, Internet of Things (IoT) and Big Data, and other recent technologies such as Blockchain. In this way, the circular economy can serve as a paradigm that directs the short, medium, and long-term sustainability of cities, and those smart cities managed according to CE principles could be considered within the emerging concept of Smart Circular Cities. Thus, in this type of city, Cloud Computing platforms will be used to manage the data collected by the sensors and sent through the Internet (IOT). These vast amounts of data will be managed through Big Data, seeking to achieve sustainability objectives. This huge wave of data brings new possibilities in the design and management of cities from both economic and social perspectives. In addition, the processing of this data through AI can contribute to an unprecedented development of the urban fabric, its sustainability, and habitability [6].

In this context, within the principles of CE inspired by the theory of human ecology, one of the most relevant is the reduction of the carbon footprint, an aspect that is closely related to the air quality of cities [4]. Technology can help us achieve a transition to a low-emissions model with a low environmental impact, which will translate into improved health for citizens [7] [4] and enhance the habitability of cities.

The main emissions in cities proceed from vehicles and are related to logistics derived from the production of industrial goods and services. The daily quality of the air in cities will depend on their identification and control. Currently, for emissions control and prevention we have both the necessary infrastructure and the technologies that allow the analysis and treatment of information with a predictive purpose.

The precise objective of this work is to develop an analytical model that, using AI algorithms, will provide predictive information allowing decisions to be made on how to improve air quality in cities. The model will be supported by infrastructure that captures the data and technologies which facilitate its management, treatment, and analysis, and also

project this data into the future, providing an intelligent air management model supported by both technology and AI.

II. SMART CITIES AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Smart City can be defined as the result of the application of innovative technologies to the efficient management and maintenance of the services and infrastructure of a city. Smart Cities pursue the generation of value by connecting infrastructure using digital technologies [1] [2] [3]. These technologies include the Internet of Things (IoT) [6], the use of Big Data [8] (Cheng et al., 2018), and AI [9]. Infrastructure includes the efficient use of networks, and the use of different types of sensors suitable for each variable to be measured; for example, the network of low-cost PurpleAir PM2.5 monitors (each with two sensors) implemented in the city of Patras [10]. Besides the use of Cloud Computing-type information management and processing infrastructure and equipment, Big Data and the ability to manage data stand out, as does the use of dashboards that report, in real time, the situations that always occur. Thus, through the proper management of the data generated, the managers will make the most appropriate decisions in the management of the analysed areas. The analysis of the generated data can be done through AI, which seeks to train computers to imitate human thought patterns and even simulate human behaviour [11]. Therefore, the ultimate goal of Smart Cities is to achieve greater efficiency in cities, providing comfort and quality of life to citizens.

Local and national governments are promoting the Smart Cities concept. Dhunny, Siew and Jones [12] point out that it is an increasingly popular concept and that there is a need to further encourage its adoption. The EU is promoting the development of Smart Cities through various programs and projects. However, many decision makers have not understood the application of technology to cities, arguing about the fear of losing control of the data, privacy problems, and other inconveniences indirectly generated by the data [13]. On the other hand, a notable concern can be observed because the automation and digitization of services in cities generate unemployment, affecting individual economic status [14].

Despite these obstacles, experts affirm that the smart city is the ideal solution to manage the challenges that arise with drastic urbanization and population growth [12]. Among these challenges, and under the principles of the EC, we find waste management, air pollution, traffic congestion, adverse effects on human health, the scarcity of resources and materials, and the aging of infrastructure [15] [16].

The application of CE principles to cities aims to improve the standard of living of the community. In the ranking exercise conducted by the Institute for Management Development with Singapore University for Technology and Design (SUTD)₁, Singapore, Helsinki, Zurich, Oslo, Amsterdam, New York, and Seoul stood out as the top 7 Smart cities of 2020. Curiously, the main outstanding characteristics of these cities were not aspects related to technological developments but to the integration of these developments and sustainability. For example, Singapore incorporates the “eco-city” programs, a city without vehicles; Helsinki formulates the goal of zero emissions in 2035, while Zurich proposes drastic reduction of the city's energy consumption. All this suggests that Smart cities must include the objective of

sustainability in their definition, giving rise to the concept of Smart Circular Cities, which are those where the smart management of cities pursues economic, social, and environmental objectives. In this concept, the technologies applied are integrated with the principles of sustainability, being a paradigm that can reorient this management model towards the CE.

From all of the above we can affirm that circularity is a differentiating characteristic of certain Smart Cities, which allows us to speak of "Smart Circular Cities". According to Núñez-Cacho et al. [17], CE addresses a series of dimensions such as energy management, management of materials, water, emissions, waste, and aspects related to the 3 R's (reduce, reuse, and recycle). All of these can be applied to the management model of smart cities, making them authentic Smart Circular Cities.

III. THE PROBLEM OF THE AIR QUALITY IN SMART CIRCULAR CITIES

Of the different dimensions addressed by CE, in this work we focus on one of them: the control of CO₂ emissions. Within this, a key aspect is air quality. The control of this indicator relates to the total volume of CO₂ emissions, in accordance with the Paris agreements of 2015 restricting emission quotas. On the other hand, air quality affects the health of citizens, and is therefore a major concern for cities. Crane et al. [4] state that a healthy and sustainable city is one that allows all people, communities, and natural systems to prosper now and in the future. The authors include the physical, socioeconomic, and ecological dimensions of the city.

AI and Machine Learning (ML) are especially useful technological resources to address the problem of air quality management and the prediction of future behaviour. Thus, Kapoor et al. [18] analysed air quality through a pilot study in which various measurements in a building were used as data and based on this system, analysed the predictive capacity of several ML algorithms, such as the artificial neural network (ANN), support vector machine (SVM), decision tree (DT), Gaussian process regression (GPR) and optimized GPR, linear regression (LR), and ensemble learning (EL). The prediction of the SVM quadratic algorithm showed a good fit, also the DT, although the best of them was the optimized GPR.

Cities that seek to intelligently control air quality must, first of all, have a measurement infrastructure, made up of wireless sensor networks that measure various air quality parameters, such as SO₂, NO_x, O₃, Benzene, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, metals, etc. These sensors must communicate with each other and incorporate a self-sufficient and low-cost microcontroller that allows managing the flow of data from the sensors and storing and/or processing them [19]. This system is connected to a central hub, usually supported by Cloud Computing technologies. On the other hand, the factors affecting air pollution to be measured must be defined: traffic and transport, economic activity, or climatology [20]. Thus, based on the series of data obtained and the information generated from them, the AI algorithms allow the data to be analysed and a predictive pattern to be created using a model that shows the future trend of air quality, which will allow those responsible to make decisions related to this aspect.

IV. PREDICTIVE MODEL OF AIR QUALITY IN THE SMART CIRCULAR CITIES

To analyse the problem of air quality management in cities, we start from the work of Ruiz-Guerra et al. [21], in which the case of the city of Barcelona is presented. This Spanish city's AQ parameters are triple the new air quality reference values set by the World Health Organization (WHO), according to the 2021 Barcelona pollution report₂.

To control the air quality, the city has a surveillance and prevention network that has twenty-five measurement points in the Barcelona metropolitan area. The data available are: SO₂, NO_x, O₃, PM₁₀, Metals, Benzene, and PM_{2.5}, among others_{3, 4,5}. The ICQA air quality index is formed using a combination of the levels of these.

Ruiz-Guerra et al. [21] highlighted the influence of tourism on Barcelona's air quality indices. Based on the data analysed from monthly measurement series over 12 years, including on the one hand the information on SO₂, NO_x, O₃, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} from sensors near the port of Barcelona, and on the other hand the time series of cruise tourism travellers of the 144 periods analysed, a regression model was established in which the dependent variable was the air quality index, and the predictor variables were the number of travellers and the number of cruises, as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. SUMMARY OF THE FIT OF THE MODEL PRESENTED BY RUIZ-GUERRA et al. (2019)

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.674 ^a	0,454	0,446	0,74421423	0,984

a. Predictors: (Constant), CRUISES, PASSANGERS b. Dependent Variable: REGR factor score 1 for analysis 1

Source: Ruiz Guerra et al. [21]

As a result, a predictive equation was generated in which the number of passengers appears as a predictive variable in the next equation:

$$EI = - 6,15e-06 + 0.036 * Passengers$$

The model is useful, although it is true that it also has limitations. For example, you need to incorporate more predictor variables and process all the data through ML, in order to establish a more complete predictive model that fits the actual behaviour of the air quality index. Despite these limitations, this work [21] can serve as a basis for the development of an integration model for air quality measurement in the predictive systems of Smart Cities, considering them, in this way, as Smart Circular Cities.

We intend to develop a predictive system that allows decision makers to anticipate air quality management. The information that would be incorporated into the model, regarding air quality, is available on the website of the Statistical Institute of Catalonia. It comes from twenty-five stations (Table 2) that record more than ten pollutants, from carbon monoxide (CO) to benzene or heavy metals. The sensors do not control the emitting sources but monitor the concentration levels of pollutants in the air at certain points

in the city. The sensors are located at representative points of diverse types of roads and are divided into three types: urban background stations, suburban stations, and traffic stations.

TABLE 2: NETWORK OF ENVIRONMENTAL SENSORS IN BARCELONA CITY.

Nº	Location	Automatic measure	Non automàtic measure
1	Badalona (Assemblea de Catalunya)		PM10
2	Badalona (Mont-roig - Ausiàs March)	SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃	
3	Barcelona (Ciutadella)	NO _x , O ₃	
4	Barcelona (el Poblenou)	NO _x , PM10	Benceno, B(a)P, PM10, PM2.5, Metales,
5	Barcelona (el Port Vell)		PM10
6	Barcelona (Gràcia - Sant Gervasi)	SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , CO, PM10	Benceno, B(a)P, PM10, PM2.5, Metales
7	Barcelona		B(a)P, PM10, Metales
8	Barcelona (l'Eixample)	SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , CO, PM10	Benceno, B(a)P, PM10, PM2.5, Metales
9	Barcelona (Observatori Fabra)	NO _x , O ₃ , PM10	
10	Barcelona (Palau Reial)	SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , CO, PM10, PM2.5	
11	Barcelona (parc de la Vall d'Hebron)	SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , CO, PM10	Benceno, B(a)P, PM10, PM2.5, Metales
12	Barcelona (pl. de la Universitat)		B(a)P, PM10, PM2.5, Metales
13	Barcelona (Sants)	NO _x	Benceno, B(a)P, PM10, Metales
14	Barcelona (Zona Universitària)		B(a)P, PM10, PM2.5, Metales
15	El Prat de Llobregat (CEM Sagnier)	Benceno, SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , CO	PM10, PM2.5, Metales,
16	El Prat de Llobregat (jardins de la pau)	SO ₂ , NO _x	PM10, Metales
17	Gavà	Benceno, SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , CO	PM10, PM2.5, Metaless
18	L'Hospitalet	NO _x , PM10	PM2.5
19	Molins de Rei		PM10
20	Sant Adrià de Besòs	NO _x , O ₃ , PM10	PM2.5
21	Sant Vicenç	SO ₂ , NO _x	PM10
22	Sant Vicenç		PM10, PM2.5, Metales
23	Sant Vicenç dels Horts	SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , PM10	
24	Santa Coloma	NO _x	PM10, PM2.5
25	Viladecans (Atrium)	Benceno, SO ₂ , NO _x , O ₃ , CO	PM10, PM2.5, Metales

Source: Barcelona City Council

Using this measurement system, the city collects almost continuous measurements of different air quality parameters, which can be integrated with the rest of the data received and have an influence on the environment, such as industrial production, growth of the population, tourism, situation of

thermal power plants, transport and logistics, etc. Once the information on the city has been collected, the following model is proposed for its management (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. PROPOSED MODEL FOR AIR QUALITY MANAGEMENT.

The model collects information on the various air quality parameters through the city's environmental quality sensors. Afterwards, it is transmitted through their network to the microcontrollers, which in turn transfer this information to the data servers in a Cloud Computing infrastructure enabled for it. The network follows the model proposed for environmental management by Nayibe et al. [22]. Subsequently, the data are integrated with the rest of the information from other sources on parameters that influence air quality. After that, ML is applied, processing the information through the algorithms described by Kapoor et al. [18], which are identified as the most accurate for air quality prediction. The first algorithm would be support vector machine (SVM), a moderately new concept in the field of environmental science. Researchers employing remote sensing in environmental and ecological applications initially adopted SVM, due to the rapid growth of data-intensive technologies and the accompanying gap in the development of analytical tools. Support vector classification is based on a specific form of statistical machine learning, with Vapnik support theory.

The second appropriate algorithm would be the decision tree (DT), whose approach seeks to demonstrate the links between samples and visually represent them in the form of a "phylogenetic tree". The structure represents the feature space in a hierarchical manner and helps create links between the data. The features identify the leaves of the tree and all the branches come together at the base, just as they do on a real tree. A DT, unlike a genuine tree, is usually depicted as growing from top to bottom. Starting at the root and working through the branches to a leaf that identifies the class, membership of unknown data can be determined [18]. Machine learning decision tree algorithms including ID3, C4.5, C5.0, and CART (Classification and Regression Trees) are quite powerful. ID3 and C4.5 are used in classification problems. In this context, the prediction power of these algorithms is remarkably high [23].

Subsequently, the predictions generated from the models are transferred to the dashboard that displays the information to the person in charge who will make decisions for air quality control, acting with specific measures in the short, medium, and long term.

As future lines of research, we point to the need to incorporate multiple variables into the analysis of air quality and assess the algorithms suggested here to determine their predictive capacity.

V. CONCLUSION

Smart Cities can be inspired by the principles of the circular economy to improve the quality of life and health of their citizens. When the smart cities implement the principles of CE, we can refer to them as Circular and Smart Cities. The management of energy, water, the materials used and resources, the management of waste and emissions, and the implementation of 3R's systems are dimensions that contribute to the development of this model. The control of emissions and their consequences on air quality falls within this model of circular smart cities, in which, although it is necessary to enjoy the comforts and services offered by technologies and the improvement of systems, it is essential to offer quality of life to the people who live there. Based on the study by Ruiz-Guerra et al. [20] and data collected from the city of Barcelona, a model is presented that collects in an integrated way the technological processes of air quality in smart cities and generates predictions using AI algorithms: SVM and DT. The use of AI in air quality management shows a great superiority of predictive power against estimates based on statistical regression with more limited data. Models that incorporate a large number of variables will make it possible to obtain future predictions about air quality. This will enable those responsible to make more accurate decisions, not only once the low quality of the air has been detected, but also knowing the predictions of the algorithms a priori, indicating and proposing actions in the short, medium, and long term that can avoid in future this environmental contamination of the air.

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